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Abstract

For many decades, research on the distribution of butterflies in Albania faced significant challenges due to the country's prolonged isolation. However, this situation has gradually improved, and in recent years, Albania's growing appeal as a tourist destination has opened new opportunities for entomological research. To date, two atlases have been published, but in a country that was previously underexplored and is now experiencing more comprehensive study, these printed documents quickly become outdated upon publication. A dynamic website with up-to-date data helps address this issue, though it remains essential to maintain a timestamp for each version in an official repository. The fourth version of the Atlas, which includes all observations up to 31.12.2025, is now available in the Zenodo repository, with plans for annual updates moving forward. This Atlas will also serve as the foundation for future assessments of the Albanian Red List of butterflies.

Key words

Atlas, distribution, update, 2025, Papilionoidea, butterflies, Albania, biodiversity, conservation.

Introduction

Despite numerous challenges, Prof. Katriot Misja successfully published the first comprehensive Atlas of the Butterflies of Albania in 2005. This book, however, was extremely difficult to find outside Albania. Years ago, for example, the first author was contacted by the late Dr. Kudrna, who had an extensive collection of atlases and books related to the MEB research. He inquired whether the first author could assist in acquiring a copy of the book. To address this, a [scan](#) was uploaded to the ResearchGate account of the first author, with the permission of Prof. Misja's family. Since the publication of the first Atlas, foreign entomologists have steadily increased their visits to Albania, leading to a significant increase in available data. In 2018, [Cuvelier et al.](#) published a second Atlas that compared historical records with data from two extensive surveys conducted in 2017, which resulted in the addition of three new species to Albania's list. In recent years, biodiversity websites, such as [iNaturalist](#) and [Observado](#), have shown a growing number of butterfly observations from Albania, offering significant potential to expand the country's available data. However, it is crucial to validate these observations, particularly due to the presence of numerous species that can be challenging to identify even on photographs from specimens in nature. Moreover, since different biodiversity platforms use distinct frameworks and rely solely on their own data, the maps created on these sites do not always accurately represent the distribution of local populations. In 2023, Bjerregård *et al.* announced four new species for Albania on their personal websites. Additionally, data from other recent surveys, which either added new species or confirmed previously data-deficient species, contributed to the launch of the first dynamic Atlas; marking the official launch of the [Fluturat e Shqipërisë](#) website. The announcement of the website and key discoveries were also published by [Cuvelier et al.](#) (2023). A new Atlas, including all observations up to the end of 2025 was published by [Cuvelier & Papparisto](#) (2025). As mentioned in this last Atlas and given the growing number of observations, it is essential to provide an updated version of the Atlas that includes all observations up to the end of 2025.

Atlas 2026

Historical data Additional data from the 2018 update New data since the 2018 update.
Small dot: observation needing confirmation (lacking evidence from photograph, genitalia or DNA barcoding)
The nomenclature is based on [Taymans & Cuvelier](#) (2025).

Papilionidae

[Iphiclides podalirius](#)

[Papilio alexanor](#)

[Papilio machaon](#)

[Allancastris cerisiyi](#)

[Driopa mnemosyne](#)

[*Parnassius apollo*](#)

[*Zerynthia polyxena*](#)

Hesperiidae

[*Gegeres nostradamus*](#)

[*Gegeres pumilio*](#)

[*Hesperia comma*](#)

[*Ochloides sylvanus*](#)

[*Pelopidas thrax*](#)

[*Thymelicus acteon*](#)

[*Thymelicus lineola*](#)

[*Thymelicus sylvestris*](#)

[*Carterocephalus palaemon*](#)

[*Heteropterus morpheus*](#)

Carcharodus alceae

Erynnis marloyi

Erynnis tages

Muschampia alta

Muschampia floccifera

Muschampia lavatherae

Muschampia orientalis

Muschampia tessellum

Pyrgus alveus

Pyrgus andromedae

Pyrgus armoricanus

Pyrgus carthami

Pyrgus cinarae

Pyrgus malvae

Pyrgus serratulae

[*Pyrgus sidae*](#)

[*Spialia orbifer*](#)

[*Spialia phlomidis*](#)

Pieridae

[*Colias alfajariensis*](#)

[*Colias aurorina*](#)

[*Colias caucasica*](#)

[*Colias croceus*](#)

[*Gonepteryx cleopatra*](#)

[*Gonepteryx farinosa*](#)

[*Gonepteryx rhamni*](#)

[*Leptidea duponcheli*](#)

[*Leptidea juvernica*](#)

[*Leptidea sinapis*](#)

Anthocharis cardamines

Anthocharis damone

Anthocharis gruneri

Aporia crataegi

Euchloe ausonia

Euchloe penia

Pieris balcana

Pieris brassicae

Pieris ergane

Pieris krueperi

Pieris manii

Pieris napi

Pieris rapae

Pontia chloridice

Pontia edusa

Lycaenidae

[*Lycaena alciphron*](#)

[*Lycaena candens*](#)

[*Lycaena dispar*](#)

[*Lycaena ottomanus*](#)

[*Lycaena phlaeas*](#)

[*Lycaena thersamon*](#)

[*Lycaena tityrus*](#)

[*Lycaena virgaureae*](#)

[*Agriades pyrenaica dardanus*](#)

[*Aricia agestis*](#)

[*Aricia anteros*](#)

[*Aricia artaxerxes*](#)

[*Cacyreus marshalli*](#)

[*Celastrina argiolus*](#)

[*Cupido alcetas*](#)

Cupido argiades

Cupido decolorata

Cupido minimus

Cupido osiris

Cyaniris semiargus

Eumedonia eumedon

Glaucopteryx alexis

Iolana iolas

Kretania sephirus

Lampides boeticus

Leptotes pirithous

Lysandra bellaruga

Lysandra coridon

Phengaris alcon

Phengaris arion

Plebejus argus

Plebejus argyrognomon

Plebejus idas

Polyommatus admetus

Polyommatus amandus

Polyommatus damon

Polyommatus daphnis

Polyommatus dorylas

Polyommatus eros

Polyommatus escheri

Polyommatus icarus

Polyommatus aroaniensis lurae

Polyommatus aroaniensis orphicus

Polyommatus ripartii

Polyommatus thersites

Pseudophilotes bavius

Pseudophilotes vicrama

Scolitantides orion

Tarucus balkanica

Calliphrys rubi

Favonius quercus

Satyrium acaciae

Satyrium ilicis

Satyrium pruni

Satyrium spini

Satyrium w-album

Thecla betulae

Riodinidae

[*Hamearis lucina*](#)

Nymphalidae

[*Apatura ilia*](#)

[*Apatura iris*](#)

[*Apatura metis*](#)

[*Charaxes jasius*](#)

[*Danaus chrysippus*](#)

[*Argynnis pandora*](#)

[*Argynnis paphia*](#)

[*Boloria dia*](#)

[*Boloria euphrosyne*](#)

[*Boloria graeca*](#)

Boloria pales

Boloria titania

Brenthis daphne

Brenthis hecate

Brenthis ino

Fabriciana adippe

Fabriciana niobe

Issoria lathonia

Speyeria aglaja

Libythea celtis

Limenitis camilla

Limenitis reducta

Neptis rivularis

Neptis sappho

Aglais io

Aglais urticae

Araschnia levana

Euphydryas aurinia

Euphydryas maturna

Melitaea arduinna

Melitaea athalia

Melitaea aurelia

Melitaea cinxia

Melitaea diamina

Melitaea didyma

Melitaea ornata

Melitaea phoebe

Melitaea trivia

Nymphalis antiopa

Nymphalis polychloros

Nymphalis vai-album

Nymphalis xanthomelas

Polygonia c-album

Polygonia egea

Vanessa atalanta

Vanessa cardui

Aphantopus hyperantus

Arethusana arethusa

Brintesia circe

Chazara briseis

Coenonympha arcania

Coenonympha glycerion

Coenonympha leander

Coenonympha orientalis

Coenonympha pamphilus

Coenonympha rhodopensis

Erebia aethiops

Erebia alberganus

Erebia cassioides

Erebia epiphron

Erebia euryale

Erebia gorge

Erebia liqea

Erebia medusa

Erebia melas

Erebia oeme

Erebia ottomana

Erebia pandrose

Erebia pronoe

Erebia rhodopensis

Erebia triarius

Hipparchia fagi

Hipparchia fatua

Hipparchia semele

Hipparchia senthes

Hipparchia statilius

Hipparchia syriaca

Hipparchia volgensis

Hyponephele lupinus

Hyponephele lycaon

Kirinia climene

Kirinia roxelana

Lasiommata maera

Lasiommata megera

Lasiommata petropolitana

[*Maniola jurtina*](#)

[*Melanargia galathea*](#)

[*Melanargia larissa*](#)

[*Melanargia russiae*](#)

[*Minois dryas*](#)

[*Pararge aegeria*](#)

[*Proterebia phegea*](#)

[*Pseudochazara amalthea*](#)

[*Pseudochazara amymone*](#)

[*Pseudochazara geyeri*](#)

[*Pseudochazara tisiphone*](#)

[*Pyronia cecilia*](#)

[*Pyronia tithonus*](#)

[*Satyrus ferula*](#)

Each species in the Atlas is also accessible online by family through hyperlinks in the bar below.

Papilionidae	Hesperiidae	Pieridae	Lycaenidae	Riodinidae	Nymphalidae Except Satyrinae	Nymphalidae only Satyrinae
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Discussion

The actual database contains 3,755 historical observations, with 2,357 new observations added in the 2018 Atlas. The current version is based on a total of 38,114 observations. This new Atlas, derived from recent surveys and collected opportunistic data, has recently led to numerous observations and the discovery of new localities for many species. An analysis of the database by family is presented in Table 1, displaying the numbers of Data Deficient species, confirmed species after 2018, and potentially occurring taxa. Table 2 provides an overview of the species and ESUs newly recorded since the publication of the first Atlas (Misja 2005).

Table 1. Family-based analysis of the actual database.

Number of species and ESUs per family	Full database (Data Deficient)	Confirmed after 2018	Potentially occurring
Papilionidae	7	7	
Hesperiidae	28 (1)	27	
Pieridae	25 (1)	24	
Lycaenidae	57	55	2
Riodinidae	1	1	
Nymphalidae	95 (1)	90	5

Muschampia tessellum (Hübner, [1803]), *Pontia chloridice* (Hübner, [1813]) and *Neptis rivularis* (Scopoli, 1763) have been cited in historical publications but their presence has not been confirmed since then.

There are valid reasons to question whether the first two species are actually part of the Albanian butterfly fauna, as their food plants are either absent or extremely rare and local. *M. tessellum* is a sedentary species, making it unlikely to be present in Albania in the absence of the food plants. *P. chloridice*, a butterfly known for its wandering behavior, may account for the mentioned specimens as an outlier in historical observations, occurring far from the nearest populations.

The situation with *Neptis rivularis* is different. All historical data that could be verified were found to be misidentifications or taxonomic errors, but food plants are present in Albania. Since *N. rivularis* occurs in neighboring countries, its presence cannot be entirely ruled out.

In the current [checklist](#), these three species remain listed as Data Deficient.

Cupido alceas (Hoffman[n]segg, 1804) and *Cupido decolorata* (Staudinger, 1886) have also been cited in historical publications but have not been formally confirmed, although a few female specimens of this type of *Cupido* have been recorded. Due to the challenges in identifying females of these two species, they are represented with smaller dots, reflecting the observer's provided identification.

In 2025, *Neptis sappho* (Pallas, 1771) was observed for the first time ([Cuvelier & Taymans 2025](#)), with proof from different localities and also observed without capture or photographs from a two other Albanian localities.

Pseudochazara geyeri (Herrich-Schäffer, [1846]) was confirmed (Cuvelier & Molinari 2025) since [Misja](#) (2025).

Four Nymphalidae have not been confirmed since the second Atlas: *Boloria pales* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775), *Erebia pronoe* (Esper, [1780]), *Hipparchia fatua* Freyer, [1843] and *Minois dryas* (Scopoli, 1763). These are habitat specialists found in environments that are not common in Albania and are poorly surveyed due to difficult access.

The following eight species may be discovered in the future, as their food plants are present in various mountains and regions of Albania and have been confirmed in nearby localities in neighboring countries: *Agrion pyrenaica dardanus* (Freyer, [1843]), *Pseudophilotes bavius* (Eversmann, 1832), *Limenitis populi* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Melitaea arduinna* (Esper, [1783]), *Melitaea aurelia* Nickerl, 1850, *Nymphalis vau-album* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) and *Coenonympha glycerion* (Borkhausen, 1788). The species are included in the [Checklist](#) with a notification of potentially present, and a blank map is provided in the Atlas and each monograph in [Fluturat e Shqipërisë](#).

Table 2. Newly recorded species and ESUs for Albania since the first Atlas (Misja 2005)

New species for Albania	Date of first observation	Locality	Source
<i>Cacyreus marshalli</i>	23.viii.2009	Tiranë	Sachanowicz K. <i>et al.</i> 2016.
<i>Anthocharis damone</i>	03.v.2010	Borsh	Sachanowicz K. <i>et al.</i> 2016.
<i>Melitaea diamina</i>	23.vi.2011	Lepushë	Sachanowicz K. <i>et al.</i> 2016.
<i>Polyommatus aroaniensis lurae</i>	17.vii.2013	Voskopojë	Cuvelier S. <i>et al.</i> 2023
<i>Limenitis camilla</i>	03.vii.2016	Rragam	Cuvelier S. <i>et al.</i> 2018
<i>Pyrgus andromedae</i>	28.vi.2017	Vermosh	Cuvelier S. <i>et al.</i> 2018
<i>Leptidea juvernica</i>	05.vii.2017	Cerem	Cuvelier S. <i>et al.</i> 2018
<i>Colias caucasica</i>	10.vii.2017	Vau i Cajës	Cuvelier S. <i>et al.</i> 2018
<i>Polyommatus aroaniensis orphicus</i>	19.vii.2017	Valikardhë	Parmentier <i>et al.</i> 2022
<i>Boloria titania</i>	05.vii.2017	Cerem	Cuvelier S. <i>et al.</i> 2018
<i>Pseudochazara tisiphone dibra</i>	13.vii.2017	Bulqizë	Cuvelier S. & Marafi M. 2025
<i>Satyrium pruni</i>	24.vii.2018	Guri i Vashës	Parmentier L. 2018
<i>Araschnia levana</i>	08.vii.2019	Gocaj, Valbonë	Cuvelier <i>et al.</i> 2023
<i>Euphydryas maturna</i>	06.vii.2019	Gocaj, Valbonë	Cuvelier <i>et al.</i> 2023
<i>Erebia albergana</i>	07.vii.2019	Kukaj, Valbonë	Cuvelier <i>et al.</i> 2023
<i>Proterebia phegea</i>	26.iv.2022	Vau-Dejës	Prendi <i>et al.</i> 2023
<i>Heteropterus morpheus</i>	29.vi.2023	Has district	Fluturat e Shqipërisë 2023
<i>Pelopidas thrax</i>	20.ix.2024	Sarandë	Fluturat e Shqipërisë 2024
<i>Neptis sappho</i>	23.vi.2025	Bushtriçë	Cuvelier S. & Taymans M 2025

Although the map (Fig. 1) may give the impression of comprehensive coverage across Albania, the reality is that with a database of 38,114 observations spanning a land area of 28,748 km², this amounts to barely 1,3 butterflies per square kilometer. The map also fails to account for the variety of habitat types across different altitudes, with the alpine level being particularly undersurveyed due to difficult access. Additionally, it does not reflect temporal factors, as the tourist summer season is overrepresented, while early spring is poorly surveyed.

Fig. 1. Coverage map 31.xii.2025. (© Sylvain Cuvelier & Anila Papparisto)

At present, tracking changes in distribution for some butterfly species in Albania remains challenging due to various factors. While some species may be expanding or experiencing potential declines, the current dataset and monitoring efforts are limited by gaps in survey coverage, particularly at higher altitudes and during certain seasons, such as early spring. Furthermore, the lack of comprehensive surveys in specific habitats and regions makes it difficult to accurately track distribution patterns. Additionally, the impact of climate change on species distribution is an emerging concern. Shifts in temperature and seasonal weather patterns may be causing species to move to higher altitudes or new areas, further complicating tracking efforts. Habitat fragmentation and human activities, such as land use changes and urbanization, also pose significant threats to species' ability to maintain stable populations in certain regions. As such, more robust data collection and future surveys are essential for understanding the full distribution dynamics of species, including those on the Red List, to detect both potential expansions and declines. Enhanced monitoring efforts, taking into account environmental changes, will be key to accurately assessing species' current status and informing effective conservation strategies.

The analysis of the previous Atlas has led to significant reclassifications in the proposals for a future version of the Albanian Red List of Butterflies, compared to the previous editions (2006, 2013, and 2022). The potential reclassifications were included and are available for consultation in a table that compares the Red Lists, the proposals based on this Atlas, and eight notes that group cases of different species in [Paparisto & Cuvelier](#) (2025).

With the actual Atlas, such adaptations were not included.

Conclusion

Although the volume of annual observation data is in no way comparable to the vast amounts of data collected in Northwestern European countries, there has been a noticeable increase in recent years. Given the limitations in the coverage of butterfly data from Albania, regular updates are crucial not only for expanding knowledge and tracking potential changes, but also for refining a future Red List to better reflect on-the-ground conditions and support more effective conservation efforts. The static nature of Red Lists is a flaw that slows timely action, especially as

butterfly decline accelerates due to habitat loss and climate change.

These facts support the dynamic purpose of the [Atlas](#) on the Fluturat e Shqipërisë website through yearly updates, while also emphasizing the need for a repository of versions, which is being addressed here within the framework of the EU repository Zenodo.

In conclusion, effective monitoring, considering both environmental changes and human impacts, is crucial for accurately tracking butterfly species' distribution dynamics in Albania and for informing future conservation efforts.

We reiterate the request to share all Albanian butterfly observations in order to enhance our understanding of their distribution and to update and refine the future versions of the Atlas, Red List and more effective conservation initiatives.

Author contributions

Both authors contributed to the conceptualization, field work, data collection, writing, manuscript preparation, literature review, and reference compilation. The first author took the lead in data analysis and interpretation, mapping, as well as the verification and validation of species. Both authors also participated in editing the manuscript.

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